

De-constructing the Problematique of Kashmir Conflict and Repeal of Articles 370

Uzma Naz, Sajjad Ali, Tariq Javed Akhtar

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01 ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: August 02,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : De-construction, Kashmir,Conflict,Article 370, Human Rights</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16729244</p>	<p><i>Conflict is ubiquitous. In the contemporary world of dependency and interdependency, we have to live with it. Competition, cooperation, and conflict will remain essential components of regional and global emerging order. Confronted with such an emerging world where does Pakistan stand on the issue of Kashmir. This paper will first examine the historical sources of the Kashmir dispute and then move on to examine the Musharraf formula to resolve what appears to be the never-ending Conflict of Kashmir. We shall use the third-party intervention model to examine the possibility of resolving the conflict.</i></p>

Introduction

Pakistan and India got their independence in 1947. Since its inception, Pakistan's foreign policy has always remained affected by its rivalry with India on the issue of Jammu and Kashmir. Both the countries are facing challenges in connection with their respective foreign policies. During this research, we shall analyze the policies and the era of President General Musharraf towards the Kashmir dispute. We shall discuss the adopted policy followed by the Indian government's annulment of Article 370 of the Indian constitution. Its first part, in particular, reviews President Musharraf's plans to prevent the freedom movement from being labeled "terrorist" and his wishes to settle the problem by peaceful means. The central theme of this research is about the reforms that civilian governments have initiated and predict future developments.

Over the past seven and a half decades, Kashmir has been the most prominent cause of hostility between India-Pakistan (Korbel, 2002). Both the countries have different points of view and different objectives as it relates to Kashmir. Both countries interpret and see this issue according to their national interest. But Indian policies over this dispute have been always alarming. According to United Nations Security Council (UNSC) resolutions, Pakistan believes in the right of self-determination of the people of Jammu and Kashmir. But from the beginning, India is trying to crush the people of Kashmir. Pakistan claims the freedom of Kashmir as the logical interpretation of the Two-Nation Theory which clearly stated that the Subcontinent's Hindus and Muslims were two nations.

Research questions

- (1) What are the major causes of conflict in Kashmir?
- (2) Will the application of a third-party intervention model help the resolution of the Kashmir conflict?
- (3) Is peace an essential component of economic development and prosperity?

Research methodology

Our research methodology will be a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. For the qualitative method, we shall rely on contemporary research journals. We will also rely on the work of some contemporary scholars who have published books on Kashmir. A good example is the work of Josef Korbel. We shall also interview some key and important individuals from foreign offices and the armed forces to examine the problematics of perception and misperception in state conflict.

Theoretical Framework

Our theoretical model will be based on the role of third-party intervention in any given conflict.

The genesis of the Problem

The Charter of Independence enunciated by the British rulers laid down that out of the areas under their direct subjugation, the Muslim majority areas, for example, Punjab, Sindh, K.P.K., and Baluchistan in the North-West and East Bengal and Sylhet in the East would constitute Pakistan. The Hindu majority areas would form India.

Regarding the princely states of India, the policy was that those would take the decision themselves; to join India or Pakistan or remain independent. Kashmir was one of them. It signed a standstill agreement with India and Pakistan. Later, India entered its regular army in Kashmir and threatened Maharaja Hari Singh to sign an illegal document of accession of Kashmir with India. Seventy-two percent of the population of Kashmir was Muslim which vehemently rose against the ruler's decision.

Helped by the civilian volunteers from Pakistan, they got part of Kashmir liberated. Resultantly, there was war between the newly organized Pakistani forces and the Indian army. Suffering territorial and human losses, Nehru took the case to United Nations Security Council. The Security Council passed a resolution to hold the plebiscite in Kashmir to let the people of Kashmir decide their future. It was a historical event in the history of Kashmir. Indian attitude remained non-cooperative and it did not help the United Nations to succeed in its mission. After that the United Nations established an independent commission to resolve the issue but the Indian intransigence did not assuage and the commission remained unsuccessful.

Geo-Political Importance

The Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah termed Kashmir Jugular vein of Pakistan which simply means that Pakistan cannot exist without it. Sans Kashmir, Pakistan is incomplete (Sattar, 2019). The Mountains of Kashmir which stand as sentinels on the north eastern border of Pakistan, their denial to Pakistan seriously weakens the defence of Pakistan. Major rivers which are the backbone of our agriculture originate from Kashmir. In 1947 almost all entries into and exits from Kashmir mouthed towards Pakistan.

The latest development is the mapping of major rail and road routes of the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) which will be running through Gilgit-Baltistan. The most important of all these is the right of self-determination of the 22 million people of Kashmir. In all fairness, it must be granted to them. Fundamentally, because of Kashmir, there have been many wars between India and Pakistan for example 1948 Kashmir War, the 1965 War, the 1971 War, the 1984 Siachin War, and the 1999 Kargil War.

Arms Race between India and Pakistan.

After the war of 1971, India held a nuclear explosion in 1974. It was the climax of the arms race in the region. After the Indian initiative, Pakistan was forced to initiate the nuclear program for its survival. As we all know the survival of a state is the prime motive of all the endeavors of the state. For the sake of survival, Pakistan struggled for a balance of power in the region. In May 1998 both of them shocked the international community by testing the nuclear bombs; India did it first followed by Pakistan. We can say that it was the show of the actual balance of power in the region.

Both the countries did not sign the nuclear non-proliferation treaty which is known as NPT. Because of threats from India Pakistan does not want to stop preparation of the nuclear weapons (Ghosh, 2020). The international superpowers also want to sell their weapons by hook or by crook, that's why they want to see hostility between the two continue. If we talk about India's foreign policy we infer that they are not ready to accept Pakistan at any cost.

According to the statement of Indra Gandhi, "they want to undo Pakistan" (Korbel, 2002). And another political leader Rajeev Gandhi also declared that they will make Pakistan part of India soon. Pakistani leaders and Pakistan's foreign policy did not boast to crush India or to make it part of Pakistan. Pakistan always wanted peace and peaceful coexistence. Pakistan's foreign policy is based on bilateral peaceful relations with India and always wants to negotiate on the issue of Kashmir.

Pakistan's nuclear development is defensive and peaceful because Pakistan never tried to attack India first. This policy shows that we want to live peacefully in the region. We want to utilize our limited resources on the development of the state. Because of Indian policies, both the countries are securing their state boundaries but in securing and snatching or depriving the taxpayers of two times meal: hence, in fact making them insecure. There are many types of evils today, we have illiteracy, hunger, poverty, inflation, Covid-19, energy crisis, and other diseases, etc. to fight for but our concentration particularly is on traditional security.

Covid-19 has unveiled the development policies of both countries. This crisis unveiled the health and medical showcases. Today the people are dying because of a lack of oxygen cylinders and medicines but in both countries especially in India the lack of hospital beds the people are helpless and hopeless. In India patients of Corona virus are lying in cars and on footpaths as well. The citizens of both countries are asking about their health facilities. But it is a big question mark on the whole world's economic and development policies.

We are living in a country where about half of the people cannot read in any language. Many issues must be addressed i.e. religious activism, judicial activism and prejudice in society. Both the states are increasingly dependent upon their nuclear capability. Every state knows about "Mutual Assured Destruction" (MAD) but is continuing to spend on hard power for the sake of security. We know that war or military solution is not the way to solve our problems. We will have to sit at the table for a peaceful talk and get out of this arms race. Though we cannot say that we are living in a beautiful world yet to think that armies will solve our problems and weapons and military activities will make the situation more peaceful than we are living in a fool's paradise.

Kashmir is the bone of contention between the two states. India raised huge armed forces and finally went nuclear to realize her hegemonic designs. In turn, Pakistan had no other option and had to have a strong army. In response to India, to ensure its security, it was constrained to develop its deterrent nuclear capability also. The Kashmiris have been struggling against Indian occupation for the last 74 years. In this research, we shall try to analyze the policies of General Musharraf's government and dilate upon various options which were considered plausible at that time.

General Musharraf's Policies over Kashmir:

According to the book 'ISI of Pakistan, in July 2001 General Musharraf visited India, and a summit meeting took place between General Musharraf and Mr. Vajpayee (Kiessling,2016).The visit is considered the first solid step to improve bilateral relations. Both the leaders General Musharraf and Atal Behari Vajpayee came on the same point of starting talks on every issue which could spark hostilities. The hardliners and opposition opposed India and criticized Vajpayee's initiative to resolve the conflict between the two countries. On the other hand, Pakistan presented the Kashmir problem as the core issue.

President Musharraf again visited India to meet the Prime Minister of India in 2002. During the visit, General Musharraf raised the issue of Kashmir in a very peaceful manner. He highlighted many advantages of Kashmir's solution. In the end, he concluded that without resolving the Kashmir issue we cannot think about peaceful coexistence. We can say that he presented the Détente policy which meant 'live and let live. He also pointed out that fighting does not resolve the problem and we must endeavor to solve it by peaceful means. He urged the Indian government to open channels of mutual dialogue because both countries have wasted enough resources on fighting in the war. We must spend our limited resources on food, health, and the welfare of the people.

Various options were considered in Musharraf Era.

The governments of India and Pakistan realize that the present contentious situation cannot be allowed to go on. As a result of backdoor diplomacy, the following options were considered.

Option 1:

Jammu, the Valley, and Laddakh were awarded to India, Azad Kashmir, and Gilgit-Baltistan was given to Pakistan, and the control line was declared as the border between India and Pakistan.

Option 2:

India and Pakistan to withdraw their forces and plebiscite are held to grant the right of self-determination to the people of Kashmir following resolutions of the United Nations Security Council.

Option 3:

Jammu and Laddakh were given to India. Azad Kashmir and Gilgit-Baltistan to Pakistan and the valley is given independence.

Option 4:

The whole of Kashmir is granted independence. Pakistan and India to guarantee its freedom.

Option 5:

Jammu and Laddakh were given to India, Azad Kashmir, and Gilgit Baltistan to Pakistan, and plebiscite is held in the Valley to grant it the right of self-determination to join India or Pakistan.

Critique

There are pros and cons of all options. We can recommend Option 2 which already enjoys the approval of the UNSC. The right of self-determination must be granted to the people of Kashmir which has legal and moral justification. Alas! Some invisible hands sabotage the efforts made by both sides by creating disruptions with incidents like the Mumbai attacks.

Indians have deployed about 9 lac of regular military troops to control the Kashmiris. Their forces have been brutally massacring the Kashmiris and they have suffered about 100,000 dead for the sacred national cause in the last about 30 years. Crossing all morals human and legal limits, India has annulled Article 370 of its constitution in August 2019. The Indian government has repealed decades-old laws that provided the controversial Muslim-majority state some autonomy. Interior Minister of India told parliament that the president had signed a decree removing Article 370 of the constitution, ending Kashmir's long-standing autonomy.

What is Article 370?

Article 370 which came into effect in 1949, gives a special status to Jammu and Kashmir State in the Indian constitution (Aljazeera, 2019). It authorizes Kashmir to make its laws in all matters except finance, defence, foreign affairs, and communications. It permits Jammu and Kashmir to have a separate flag and denies property rights in Kashmir to outsiders.

That means the residents of the state live under different laws from the rest of the country in matters such as property ownership and citizenship. These lines have been taken from the Aljazeera article. After the annulment of the article, the people of Kashmir are facing forceful lockdown and curfew on daily basis since 05 August 2019. They are facing bloodshed by the Indian government. On the other hand, Pakistan supports Kashmiris in their just struggle but the world conscience is silent and they don't take the issue seriously.

The annulment of these articles is aimed at bringing major demographic changes which will help realize notorious designs of India in the future. So far the world conscience is asleep in this respect and the situation in Kashmir is aggravating day by day. Pakistan is trying to provide political and moral support to the Kashmiri brothers in their just struggle to attain their right to self-determination. We are required to redouble our efforts to harness the support of the UN, EU, OIC, big powers, and other countries to force India to let the Kashmir problem be resolved in conformity with the UNSC resolutions.

Human Rights Situation in Kashmir

Since 1947 Indian governments have been denying human rights to Kashmiris. The people of Kashmir are facing tyranny because of their demands for the right to self-determination and freedom from Indian occupation. The use of force by Indian forces is fuelling intense aggression in Kashmir. The abusive attitude and violation of human rights are becoming more and more tyrant and it is giving more impetus to the struggle for self-determination of the people of Kashmir. We can say that India is blaming the victims with the help of its strong media and is trying to construct an image of Kashmir as an integral part of India.

Indian governments always claimed that the invisible hands and cross-border militants were fuelling the situation of conflict and the situation of the war (Sifton, 2019). According to John Sifton, Human Rights Watch a director of an advocacy group, the situation of human rights in Kashmir is alarming. The Indian army wants to crush the protesters with an iron hand. The Indian security forces are using lethal force on protesters including the use of different weapons like pellet guns and tear-gas etc. These types of attacks have brutally injured Kashmiri people and many thousands have lost their lives. According to Human Rights Watch, India's "Armed Forces Special Powers Act" which is known as (AFSPA) is continuously empowering the forces who get undue immunity from any type of accountability. On the other hand, the Pakistan government is always raising its voice on the Kashmir issue but the international institutions and community are silent. We can say that they are not taking the Pakistani stance seriously.

Right to life

The Indian governments have been violating the human rights which are enunciated in the UN charter. The Indian security forces are not giving any space and even the right to life to the Kashmiris. Unfortunately, the UN and big powers are silent. According to the human rights declaration, man is born free and nobody has the right to deprive him of the liberty of life. Unfortunately, Kashmiris are facing lethal attacks at the hands of Indian security forces. According to the charter of human rights declaration, no one has the right to torture others because everyone is born free. In the case of Kashmir, the Indian security forces are torturing the Kashmiris to become Hindu and accept India as the motherland and if they become part of India only then they would be allowed to live with peace.

The Kashmiri "Hurriyat Leaders" (freedom fighters) like Syed Ali Geelani, Mirwaiz Umer Farooq, and Yaseen Malik have been tortured to make them give up their freedom movement. General Musharraf during his interview especially mentioned Yaseen Malik who many a time has faced intense torture by the Indian forces due to which he has lost his eyesight. The Kashmiri women are brutally raped and tortured. In Kashmir sometimes Indian security forces do not allow Kashmiris to perform religious activities like Friday prayer and Eid prayer etc. The Indian government has not been ready to give ordinary social rights to the Kashmiris which are laid down in the declaration of human rights of the UN. They are living discriminatory life in the so-called civilized and modern world.

The Kashmiris are paying a big price for freedom and mostly they are detained because they want freedom. They demand equal rights and they demand self-determination. Sometimes they are brutally beaten or sometimes killed whenever they show their solidarity with Pakistan. After the annulment of Article 370, Indian forces have become more lethal and tyrant. According to the HRW's reports, the Indian government has shut down Internet services, mobile phone services, and other forms of communication like social media and print media, etc. The Indian policies do not allow the Kashmiris the right to freedom of speech. They are simply denied the right to protest which is everyone's fundamental right. They are deprived of their respect Kashmiri women are raped by the Indian forces. India boasts about being the biggest democracy in the world but does not give basic human rights to its citizens, particularly Kashmiris. HRW and other forums raise their concerns about these tragedies. They emphasize upon India to grant to its citizens the right of freedom of speech.

5th Generation War:

"Fifth-generation warfare (5GW) is the battle of perceptions and information. 5GW is also a cultural and moral war, which distorts the perception of the masses to give a manipulated view of the world and politics". These lines have been taken from Aljazeera, 2021. 5GW simply means to make the impossible the possible, and possible the impossible. It is the war of information. It is the war of perception and misperception. The research came out as a result of a more than 15-years campaign involving more than 500 false news sources and a dozen fake non-governmental organizations that took place in 116 countries. The important part of our research is that many of those networks attempted to promote a pro-India and anti-Pakistan perception. The problem with this argument is that "fifth-generation war" is not a commonly known concept by international affairs or international security intellectuals. The term "fifth-generation war" does not appear in the content of five well-

regarded international relations or international security peer-reviewed journals – International Security, Journal of Conflict Resolution, Journal of Peace Research, Journal of Strategic Studies, and Security Studies—in the last five years, even though these journals have printed roughly five million words.

Criticality of the Kashmir Problem

The book “Danger in Kashmir” is the matchless treasure of knowledge about the issue of Kashmir (Korbel, 2002). None with comparable qualification and experience other than him has left such a remarkable account of the problem. Korbel says that this is the core problem that separates India and Pakistan and has resulted in many wars between the two. He adds that besides the casualties during the wars, about 10 million people migrated across the border, and about a million were killed during the partition of the sub-continent. In this situation of animosity, the UN intervened on the Indian request to decide whether Kashmir should join Pakistan or India. In the end, the author almost concludes that it was India that did not do its duty to get the plebiscite held in Kashmir.

Conclusion

Today India and Pakistan are securing their state boundaries but securing human beings and depriving innocent people of two times meals. There are many types of evils today; we have illiteracy, hunger, poverty, inflation, Covid-19, energy crisis, and other diseases, etc. which India and Pakistan must fight against. We are living in countries where half of the people cannot read in any language. Many issues must be addressed i.e. religious activism, judicial activism, and prejudice in society. The Kashmir problem is arguably the most important political problem in the world which needs to be resolved urgently. No other problem concerning the future of about 22 million people in the world is pending for so long a period. This is the oldest problem on the agenda of the United Nations. Nowhere else in the world, so much of human blood has been spilled and human lives lost as for the just right of self-determination in Kashmir. Because no other area on the planet, there are chances of breaking out of the nuclear war as much as in the case of Kashmir. These all facts entail that the world conscience must wake up from slumber and attend to the moral and political call of the hour. The UN, OIC, other international organizations, regional forums, big powers, and the world community, in general, must meet their obligations to resolve the Kashmir problem in a just and equitable manner.

References

- Korbel, J. (2002). *Danger in Kashmir*. Oxford University Press.
- Sattar, A. (2019). *Pakistan's foreign policy, 1947-2016: a concise history*. Oxford University Press.
- GHOSH, P. E. U. (2020). *International Relations*. PHI LEARNING.
- Korbel, J. (2002). *Danger in Kashmir*. Oxford University Press.
- Kiessling, H. G. (2016). *Faith, unity, discipline: the Inter-Service-Intelligence (Isi) of Pakistan*. C. Hurst & Company.
- Al Jazeera. (2019, August 5). Kashmir's special status: Five things to know. *India News | Al Jazeera*. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/8/5/kashmir-special-status-explained-what-are-articles-370-and-35a>.
- Anwardawn. (2019, November 19). Indian repression fuelling militancy in held Kashmir, warns HR watchdog. *DAWN.COM*. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1517598>.
- Butt, A. I. (2021, January 4). Has a 'fifth-generation war' started between India and Pakistan? *Cybersecurity News | Al Jazeera*. <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2021/1/4/are-india-and-pakistan-in-a-fifth-generation-war>.
- Korbel, J. (2002). *Danger in Kashmir*. Oxford University Press.

Author Information

Dr. Uzma Naz

Assistant Professor, Minhaj University Lahore

Sajjad Ali

Lecturer/Ph.D Scholar, Minhaj University Lahore

Tariq Javed Akhtar

Ph.D. Scholar, Minhaj University Lahore
